

BioValue

Benchmark for integration of biodiversity in Environmental Assessment Instruments, including chapter on test at 200 EAs from Denmark, Germany, Spain and Portugal.

D2.1 Extended version: Benchmark of the best practice of EAI in relation to biodiversity WP2 (Task 2.1), including chapter: Test of benchmark at 200 EAs from Denmark, Germany, Spain and Portugal (Task 2.2).

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1: Original version, 2: Chapter 6 on test of benchmark

This report and its contents are an expression of the authors' knowledge and conclusions and do not necessarily represent all BioValue partners. This is the first version of the report, it will be revisited and revised at later stages in the project.

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Extended version – test of the benchmark at 200 EAs

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3. Introduction

"The essence of benchmarking is the process of identifying the highest standards of excellence for products, services, or processes, and then making the improvements necessary to reach those standards - commonly called "best practices" (Bhutta and Huq, 1999 p. 254).

The BioValue project aims to safeguard and increase biodiversity through transformative change in spatial policy-making, planning practices and infrastructure development, upscaling opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of EU strategic actions on biodiversity, particularly, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030. IPBES (2019) recognises the relevance of comprehensive environmental assessments instruments (EAI), such as environmental impact assessment (EIA) and strategic environmental assessment (SEA), as supporting instruments to mitigate the impacts of development activities on biodiversity and ecosystems to promote cross-sectoral approaches constructing pathways towards sustainability aligning with the SDGs. IPBES also states that EAI are crucial for spatial planning, proposing that they can play a role in guaranteeing more integrated, resilient, and sustainable outcomes of planning processes. Also, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 indicates that to enable transformative change for European biodiversity, it is imperative to commit, implement and enforce (and where necessary review and revise) EU environmental legislation, where both the EIA and SEA Directives are included.

This benchmark reported is carried out in line with the purposes of the BioValue project. The specific purpose of the benchmark is to:

- A. Identify the current best practice guidance of integrating biodiversity into EAI especially related to spatial planning (the main purpose of this report).
- B. Compare the current best practice guidance to the current actual practice with the aim of improving the practice (comparison that will be made in Task 2.2).
- C. Establish an improved best practice guidance.

This report documents the first part of the benchmark exercise relating to the first part of the purpose (A). Here, a benchmark is derived from twelve guidance documents focussed on biodiversity in EAI (task 2.1). The guidance documents are reviewed based on a framework of questions that are a mix of open and closed questions allowing for both structured and more grounded analysis (see table 4). Based on this, a benchmark is developed, which consists of closed questions allowing for a structured and quantitative analysis of a large number of EIA and SEA reports (task 2.2, (B). The structured and quantitative analysis is reported in the new chapter 6 in this extended version of the deliverable. Based on this and the gap analysis of task 2.4, the benchmark will be revisited, and relevant revisions will be made based on finding in literature and practice.

In the later stages in the BioValue project, this will, together with knowledge from other parts of the project be used for development of a transformed practice (C). It is relevant to mention that this last part of the purpose goes beyond the definition of benchmarking by Bhutta and Huq (1999), as the BioValue project is not only concerned with development to reach the current best practice but to push much further, towards defining a new transformed practice.

The new chapter of the extended deliverable, chapter 6 in this version, contains use and test of the developed benchmark for best practice of EAI in relation to biodiversity as developed in the first part of the deliverable report (the original D2.1).

This commences with a mapping, analysis, and benchmarking of EA practices, aimed at unveiling the potential influences of EA on spatial planning and project design outcomes. Specifically, the study examines to what extent the recent (primarily within the past 5 years) EA practices align with established best practice benchmark in biodiversity integration. The benchmark indicators used for the examination in this report are a synthesized list of benchmark indicators, based on an analysis of a range of guidelines from international organizations. The indicators will be briefly recapped when used in the benchmark analysis, chapter 2 of the annex report.

The focal point lies in the examination of 201 EIA and SEA reports, which encapsulate diverse spatial planning initiatives and infrastructural development across terrestrial and marine domains in four countries within Europe: Denmark, Germany, Portugal, and Spain. The reports are selected based on four criteria; 1 The reports relate to activities at sea and activities on land, 2 The reports for EIA must cover projects with extensive land use/land conversion, 3 The SEA reports must cover plans related to spatial planning and 4 The reports must (primarily) date 5 years back. This will ensure a number of examples of SEA and EIA reports with examples of how the benchmark indicators are handled in practice in the countries. Through a textual analysis, the degree to which biodiversity considerations are integrated within these reports are scrutinized, and potentials for strengthening the practice is discussed.

The new chapter 6 contains three parts. Chapter 6.1 presents the included reports, describing their distribution across EIA and SEA, geographic region, on-shore or off-shore. Chapter 6.2 explores the analysis of biodiversity integration within the reports vis-à-vis the established BioValue benchmark, and thus revealing implications for EA practice and stimulating constructive discourse. Finally, chapter 6.3 provides an overview of the methodological framework for selecting reports and operationalise the benchmark for analysis of EA reports.

4. The benchmark for integration of biodiversity in EAI

4.1. Integration of biodiversity in decision-making and spatial planning through EAI – an EU perspective

As stated, EAI (notably EIA and SEA), have an important role in assessing the impacts of spatial policy and planning proposals on biodiversity. EIA and SEA are used at various decision-making levels for different sectors and activities and should constitute a comprehensive assessment of the total impacts on local biodiversity - and should protect it from deteriorating incrementally. This role of EIA and SEA is recognised at regional level by the European Union (as seen previously by the EU Biodiversity Strategy) as well as at international level (like IPBES).

In 2019 the EU published a guidance on the Integration of ESS in decision-making processes, based on the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2020 and the European Action Plan for Nature, People and the Economy (COM(2017) 198 final). The guidance identifies EAI, such as SEA and EIA, as supporting instruments for the integration of biodiversity and ESS in policy formulation, in planning, and in the development of large projects. They identify EAI instruments, specifically, as supporting integration of knowledge and values in decisions, into spatial planning across all sectors, and subsequent infrastructure development. For SEA, it stated that: *“SEA should help to build biodiversity and ecosystem services objectives into land use, urban and sectoral policies, plans and programmes, (...) identify and manage apparently minor impacts which may pose severe threats to biodiversity, (...) identify alternatives and mitigation strategies”*.

It has been suggested that EAI should integrate the concept of ‘no net loss’ as a framework for assessment (e.g., Gutierrez et al. 2021) and that offsetting or compensation for impacts are much-used measures. This practice is debatable compared to a more proactive approach avoiding impacts (e.g., Larsen et al. 2018). The EU also recognised the strong potential of alignment between EAI and mitigation. Besides the fact that mitigation is one of the purposes of EIA and SEA as seen in the respective EU Directives, the 2020 Guidance on Achieving No Net Loss or Net Gain of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services is set to be a ‘complement’ to avoidance and mitigation measures established through EAI. As mentioned in this Guidance, EAI *“also require the application of the mitigation hierarchy and compensation/offsetting of unavoidable impacts on nature and environment”*.

These elements of what the expected role of EAI instruments is in the integration of biodiversity in decision-making and spatial planning supports the analysis and underlines the relevance of some elements of the benchmark.

4.2. Structure of the benchmark

Based on the above, the benchmark is a form of yardstick, against which EAs can be measured to see to what degree they comply with best practice. The guidance documents cover both SEA and EIA, and in the benchmark the term Environmental Assessment (EA) is used as a broader term covering both types of instruments. The benchmark consists of 10 themes under which there are a number of indicators of best practice for integrating biodiversity in environmental assessment instruments. The themes and indicators are summarised in table 1.

Table 1 Themes and indicators of the benchmark. These are further specified in the following sections.

Themes	Indicators
A – Role	<i>How is biodiversity integrated in the EA process? (A1)</i>
	<i>How is EA and resulting knowledge about biodiversity impacts integrated in the planning process? (A2)</i>
B - Significance	<i>What methodology is used to evaluate the significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA? (B1)</i>
	<i>Which types of parameters are relevant for evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA? (B2)</i>
C – Knowledge	<i>Which types of knowledge is used for working with biodiversity in the EA? (C1)</i>
D - Synergies and trade-offs	<i>How are synergies and trade-off between biodiversity and other sustainability aspects handled in the EA? (D1)</i>
E – Ecosystem service	<i>Which types of knowledge is used for working with biodiversity in the EA? (E1)</i>
F – Goals and Visions	<i>How should biodiversity goals and visions be integrated in EA? (F1)</i>
G – Uncertainty	<i>How should the EA process deal with ‘the unknown’/uncertainty concerning biodiversity? (G1)</i>
H – Involvement	<i>Who are involved in the integration of biodiversity in the EA? (H1)</i>
I - Mitigation and enhancement	<i>How are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA? (I1)</i>
	<i>Who are involved in the integration of biodiversity in the EA? (I2)</i>
	<i>To what degree are biodiversity impacts mitigated in EA? (I3)</i>
	<i>How are financial instruments used in the EA? (I4)</i>
J – Monitoring and follow-up	<i>How does the EA specify monitoring of biodiversity impacts? (J1)</i>
	<i>What is the monitoring of biodiversity impacts specified in the EA aimed at? (J2)</i>
	<i>What does the EA specify that monitoring of biodiversity should be used for? (J3)</i>

For each of the indicators, there are two or more possible elements or answers, and the level of compliance with the indicator and thus best practice is measured differently depending on the question.

In table 2 an overview of where the different guidance documents have contributed to the benchmark are provided.

Table 2 Overview of where the different reference documents contributed to the benchmark.

	Role	Significance	Knowledge	Synergies and trade-offs	Ecosystem services	Goals and visions	Uncertainty	Involvement	Mitigation and enhancement	Monitoring and follow-up
CBD (2006)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CBBIA - IAIA (2006)	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
CBBIA - IAIA (2007)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
BBOP (2009)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Irish EPA (2012)	✓	✓						✓	✓	✓
European Commission - EIA (2013)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
European Commission - SEA (2013)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
MFI (2015)		✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓
IAIA (2018)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
EIB (2018)	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
IAIA and GBIF (2020)	✓								✓	✓
IFC (n.d.)	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓

In the following sections, the entire benchmark is reported, including for each indicator:

- the elements,
- the rationale for having the indicator,
- And how to measure the indicator.

In the final section of this report, the methodology behind developing the benchmark is presented.

A – Role

A1 – Indicator: *How is biodiversity integrated in the EA process?*

Elements:

- *Biodiversity is integrated from an early stage in the EA process.*
- *Biodiversity is integrated throughout the EA process.*

Measurements: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

The documents emphasise that biodiversity and ecosystem services play a critical role in supporting sustainable development. EA incorporates well established procedures for collecting and interpreting information on biodiversity and ecosystem services and: “*can be used to provide a ‘before and after’ picture of the distribution, status and condition of biodiversity affected by a proposed plan or project*” (BBOP, 2009 p. 7). The guidance documents highlight that it is relevant to integrate biodiversity at all the steps of an EA process. Several documents specifically point to the necessity of integrating biodiversity from an early stage and throughout the EA process.

A2 – Indicator: *How is EA and resulting knowledge about biodiversity impacts integrated in the planning, design and decision-making process?*

Elements:

- *The EA and biodiversity considerations are integrated from an early stage in the planning or design process*
- *EA and biodiversity considerations are integrated throughout the planning or design process*
- *Mitigation measures for biodiversity are integrated in the planning or design process*
- *EA and biodiversity considerations are integrated in the decision-making process*

Measurements: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

An EA is the process of assessing a possible future activity such as a strategy, plan, or project for which there is some form of a planning or design process and a decision-making process to which the EA can contribute. The guidance documents stress that biodiversity should be considered at the earliest possible stage of planning, design and decision-making processes, and that mitigation measures should be integrated in both the planning process and the outcome. Thus, moving from a more reactive to a more proactive approach to securing ecological sustainability. A further point from the guidance documents is that the EA and biodiversity considerations should be integrated starting already at the strategic decision-making level. This point is not relevant to measure for an EA seen in isolation (such as in a benchmark) but is an important point in a wider perspective.

B – Significance

B1 - Indicator: *What methodology is used to evaluate the significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Compare impacts to reference situation/0-alternative.*
- *Compare impacts against thresholds, criteria, and targets.*
- *Compare impacts to sensitivity of impacted entity.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale: Evaluating significance is a crucial and challenging point of any EAI-process also when integrating biodiversity and thus evaluating the significance of impacts on biodiversity. In four of the guidance documents, assessment of significance is mentioned as a matter of expert judgement, while one document emphasizes the need to consult with stakeholders and factor in their values and levels of concern. In the reviewed guidance documents, different methodologies for evaluating the significance of biodiversity impacts are deemed relevant. In terms of comparing against thresholds, criteria and targets, these could be both biodiversity-specific from e.g., national biodiversity strategies, or from a broader background, such as targets and criteria from the UN SDG framework. An example of such a target from the SDG framework, which has been used in EA practice is (Boess et al. 2022): *15.5 Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species* (UN 2022). Using such a target could for example mean comparing whether an impact would degrade natural habitats, cause biodiversity loss or endanger threatened species – if yes, this indicates the significance of that impact.

B2 - Indicator: *Which types of parameters are relevant for evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Parameters related to characteristics of the activity/impact on biodiversity.*
- *Parameters related to characteristics of the impacted biodiversity entities.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

The documents point to many parameters of importance when evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts including the risk of extinction of populations, species etc.; biological resources of value/use to local population; resilience of the impacted resource, area, habitat, species etc.; size, frequency, reversibility, likelihood, certainty, and duration of the impact; and protected, sensitive or valuable areas, habitats, species etc. These parameters overall cover two types of parameters namely those related to characteristics of the activity or impact and those related to the characteristics of the impacted entities.

C - Knowledge

C1 - Indicator: *Which types of knowledge is used for working with biodiversity in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Expert knowledge.*
- *Multidisciplinary knowledge.*
- *Local and indigenous knowledge.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

An important issue in relation to integration of biodiversity in EAI is what types of knowledge should be used for this integration. Ten of the analysed documents underline the need to use expert knowledge, while four of them further specify a need for multidisciplinary knowledge. Eight of the documents stress the need to not only rely on expert knowledge but include local, traditional, or indigenous knowledge and in general knowledge from local stakeholders including local authorities.

D - Synergies and trade-offs

D1 - Indicator: How are synergies and trade-off between biodiversity and other sustainability aspects handled in the EA?

Elements:

1. *Acknowledging that synergies and trade-offs exist.*
2. *Identifying synergies and trade-offs.*
3. *Managing synergies and trade-offs (if relevant).*
4. *Taking trade-offs into account in decision-making (if relevant).*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Synergies and trade-offs between biodiversity and other aspects of sustainability, namely other social, cultural, economic, and environmental issues, is mentioned as an important element in six of the reviewed documents.

“It is important that there are clear criteria for taking biodiversity into account in decision-making, and to guide trade-offs between social, economic and environmental issues including biodiversity” (CBD, 2007 p- 17).

E - Ecosystem services

E1- Indicator: *How are ecosystem services used in the EA?*

Elements:

1. *Acknowledging the importance of ecosystem services.*
2. *Mapping ecosystem services.*
3. *Identifying users/beneficiaries of ecosystem services.*
4. *Assigning values to ecosystem services.*
5. *Evaluating impacts on ecosystem services from the activities.*
6. *Mitigating impacts on ecosystem services (if relevant).*
7. *Monitoring ecosystem services (if relevant).*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

According to the analysed documents conservation of ecosystem structure and functions, with the purpose of maintaining ecosystem services, should be a priority target. Mapping the ecosystem services or land-use types should take place, in consultation with stakeholders, especially vulnerable stakeholders, to determine the values of these functions for society and to determine levels of protection, conservation and monitoring.

"For ecosystem services, IA should be used to identify ways in which ecosystem extent, health, and functionality can be safeguarded or enhanced, allowing the values and benefits derived from ecosystem services to be sustained over time"
(IAIA, 2018 p. 3).

F - Goals and visions

F1- Indicator: *How are biodiversity goals and visions integrated in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Through including conservation priorities and targets from EU Biodiversity Strategy, National biodiversity strategies or other existing guidance documents (e.g., international, and national, regional, and local laws, policies, plans and strategies) in Action plans.*
- *Deciding on a 'vision', with explicit goals, objectives, desired outcomes.*
- *Through applying an ecosystem-based approach.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

The analysed documents emphasise the importance of: *“deciding on a specific ‘vision’, with explicit goals, objectives, desired outcomes and/or targets of the strategic proposal”* (CBBIA – IAIA, 2006 p. D-4). These criteria should be based on existing policy and guidance documents, such as the EU biodiversity Strategy, other biodiversity action plans, international, national, and local legislation and/or by using an ecosystem-based approach, as these conservation priorities and targets, can guide the further development of EIA screening criteria.

G – Uncertainty

G1 - Indicator: *How does the EA process deal with uncertainty concerning biodiversity?*

Elements:

1. *Ensure transparency about lack of data, gaps in knowledge, and uncertainty*
2. *Take a precautionary approach to impacts*
3. *Identify gaps in knowledge and gather additional information (if relevant)*
4. *Manage uncertainty e.g. using adaptive management, scenarios etc. (if relevant)*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Eight of the analysed documents point to the application of the precautionary approach in decision-making when there is a risk of significant harm to biodiversity. Three documents point to the importance of identifying and decreasing knowledge gaps, and six of the documents emphasize the importance of ensuring transparency by clearly stating lack of knowledge and data, uncertainty in methods, and the level of certainty in each impact prediction. In the reviewed documents, different methods for dealing with uncertainty of biodiversity impacts in the EIA process are deemed relevant.

H – Involvement

H1 - Indicator: *Who are involved in the integration of biodiversity in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Authorities,*
- *Decision-makers,*
- *Professionals,*
- *Stakeholders,*
- *General public,*
- *Local level,*
- *NGO's.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

According to the document an effective participation of relevant stakeholders is a precondition for a successful EIA. Thus, it is important early in the process to identify, bring together and establish proactive communication and involvement with all the stakeholders and environmental authorities to help identify the key issues.

Eight of the analysed documents mention the Authorities (e.g., those responsible but also affected at both international, national, sub-national and local level), two documents mention the Decision-makers, seven documents mention the Professionals (e.g., both planners, the developer, engineers, practitioners, consultancies and experts), seven documents mention the Stakeholders (both those with direct and indirect access), four documents mention the General public (both the private and public sector), six documents mention the Local level (including indigenous communities), and finally six documents mention the NGOs. Involvement of the relevant stakeholders will also help reduce uncertainty.

I - Mitigation and enhancement

I1- Indicator: *How are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?*

Elements:

- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated in accordance with the mitigation hierarchy.*
- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated based on analysis of residual impacts.*
- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated through enhancing biodiversity values.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale: Eleven of the twelve reviewed documents prescribe that mitigation should follow the mitigation hierarchy, meaning that it should be prioritized to biodiversity impacts, then to minimize biodiversity impacts and so forth. Six of the documents prescribe that mitigation measures should be chosen based on an ongoing analysis of the residual impacts on biodiversity including mitigation measures. According to eight documents, enhancement is also an important element in mitigation, according to the documents this primarily takes the form of maximizing existing biodiversity values or creating new ones.

I2 - Indicator: *To what degree are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?*

Elements:

1. *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that 'no net loss' is achieved.*
2. *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that 'net gain' is achieved.*

Rationale: Seven of the documents state that mitigation and enhancement should continue until 'no net loss' or 'net gain' of biodiversity is achieved.

Measurement: Scale where 2 is best.

I3 – Indicator: *How is the implementation of mitigation supported by financial instruments?*

Elements:

- *The necessary financial settings for implementation of mitigation measures incl. compensation/off-setting are established (if relevant).*
- *Financial incentives are provided for proponents to protect biodiversity (if relevant).*
- *Financial settings for maintenance of biodiversity are established (if relevant).*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Four of the guidance documents point out the need to support mitigation by using financial instruments. When looking in isolation at the EA process, of course this cannot be decided in the EA and it should be at an appropriate scale, i.e. an EA cannot be expected to be the basis for providing national financial schemes and legislation. However, an EA could for example be the basis for suggesting and implementing a local fund for securing maintenance of restored biodiversity after a project has been established. The importance of taking such considerations already at the time of the EA is stressed by the EIB: *“The need for funds, legal frameworks and institutional capacity to be planned well in advance so that they are in place to allow offset implementation to begin in advance of significant impacts from the project – biodiversity-related finance should therefore be discussed during the appraisal stage”* (EIB, 2018 p. 24).

J - Monitoring and follow-up

J1 - Indicator: *How does the EA specify monitoring of biodiversity impacts?*

Elements:

- *There are plans to establish monitoring of biodiversity impacts.*
- *Clear targets, indicators, and responsibilities for monitoring of biodiversity impacts are specified.*
- *Plans for monitoring are linked to sound baseline information.*
- *Plans for monitoring specify that stakeholders should be involved.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Nine of the analysed documents emphasize that it is essential to ensure management plans, programs, and systems, including specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and timely management targets and indicators, and appropriate monitoring of biodiversity impacts. Including who should be involved and responsible for monitoring and follow up.

"Monitoring (in the third biodiversity assessment phase) should be designed to detect impacts that may have been considered initially insignificant but elevate over time, to track the implementation of mitigation measures, to follow up on the effectiveness of the mitigation strategy and to identify the need for contingency arrangements or corrective actions" (EIB, 2018 p. 19).

J2 - Indicator: *What is the monitoring of biodiversity impacts specified in the EA aimed at?*

Elements:

- *Validating the predicted biodiversity impacts.*
- *Validating the outcomes of mitigation measures.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Data from biodiversity baseline assessment and monitoring plays a crucial role in understanding current and potential future impacts of development on the natural environment. Thus, the documents emphasize how the predicted biodiversity impacts, and outcomes of mitigation measures should be highlighted in the EMP and offset planning document (if produced) as it should be used as the basis for designing or scoping any monitoring program.

J3 – Indicator: *What does the EA specify that monitoring of biodiversity should be used for?*

Elements:

- *Implementing adaptive management.*
- *Building knowledge for future EAs and planning.*
- *Checking compliance with conditions for approval.*

Measurement: How many elements does the EA comply with? The more elements, the better.

Rationale:

Seven of the analysed documents point to the importance of implementing adaptive management systems to ensure that IA commitments will be met, mitigation measures will be implemented and that no net loss/net gain (NNL/NG) outcomes can be demonstrated through monitoring, auditing, and reporting. Implementing adaptive management will ensure an appropriate reaction to protect biodiversity if there are discrepancies between what was foreseen in the EA and what emerges when the activity is actually implemented. Systematic monitoring arrangements will also improve management policies and practices as the information will improve the accuracy of assessments at plan/programme review and by learning from the outcomes of previously employed policies and practices.

5. Applied methodology for the benchmark development

The benchmark is derived from best practice guidance documents using a mostly grounded approach and open coding. In the following the methodology is presented in detail:

1. The approach to choosing the guidance documents for review.
2. The process of reviewing the documents.
3. The method for coding and analysing the data.

Choosing guidance documents as basis for benchmark

The guidance documents included in building the benchmark have been selected using the following criteria:

- **Type:** Should be documents that are meant to guide practice, e.g., guidance, guidelines, principles, standards
- **Content:** Should relate to environmental impact assessment with a broad concept of environment, e.g., not stand-alone biodiversity assessment or ecological impact assessment.
- **Language:** Should be in English
- **Author/Origin:** Should be published by national, regional, or international public agencies or recognized not-for-profit organisations. This excludes for example private consultants.
- **Time:** Should be published within the last 20 years, to ensure that it is relatively current best practice.

To find relevant documents, an online search was conducted using google.com. The following combinations of keywords were used to search:

- Biodiversity, impact assessment, guidance.
- Biodiversity, impact assessment, best practice.
- Biodiversity, impact assessment, principles.

The list of results found via the search were then reviewed and documents living up to the criteria were chosen. This continued until the results became irrelevant. As a final quality assurance, the team behind the benchmark have been consulted to see if any obvious omissions had been made.

The search and selection led to the documents in table 3, which are included in the benchmark.

Table 3 Guidance documents included in the review

Title	Origin	Year of publication	Geographic reach	Type of IA	Sector
<i>Voluntary guidelines on Biodiversity-inclusive Environmental Impact Assessment</i>	UN: Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)	2006	International	EIA	Generic
<i>Guidance Document on Biodiversity, Impact Assessment and Decision Making in Southern Africa</i>	CBBIA - IAIA	2006	Southern Africa	IA	Generic
<i>Best practice guidance for biodiversity-inclusive impact assessment</i>	CBBIA - IAIA	2007	South Asia	EIA	Generic
<i>The Relationship between Biodiversity Offsets and Impact Assessment</i>	Business and Biodiversity Offsets Programme (BBOP)	2009	International	SEA and EIA	Generic
<i>Final Report: Integrated Biodiversity Impact Assessment, Streamlining AA, SEA and EIA Processes. Best Practice Guidance</i>	Irish EPA	2012	Ireland	Appropriate Assessment (AA), SEA and EIA	Generic
<i>Guidance on Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Environmental Impact Assessment</i>	European Commission	2013	EU/Europe	EIA	Generic
<i>Guidance on Integrating Climate Change and Biodiversity into Strategic Environmental Assessment</i>	European Commission	2013	EU/Europe	SEA	Generic
<i>Good Practices for Biodiversity Inclusive Impact Assessment and Management Planning</i>	Multilateral Financing Institutions Biodiversity Group	2015	International	ESIA	Generic
<i>International Best Practice Principles – Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services in Impact Assessment</i>	IAIA	2018	International	IA	Generic
<i>Guidance Note for Standard 3 on Biodiversity and Ecosystems</i>	European Investment Bank (EIB)	2018	EU/Europe	EIA and SEA	Generic
<i>Best Practices for Publishing Biodiversity Data from Environmental Impact Assessments</i>	IAIA and GBIF	2020	International		Generic
<i>A Guide to Biodiversity for the Private Sector</i>	International Finance Corporation (WB)	N.D	International	SEIA	Private sector (generic)

Review and coding of guidance documents

The chosen guidance documents were reviewed with a focus on a number of questions, which can be seen in table 4. These questions are inspired by:

- The basis and purpose of the BioValue project including discussions with the partners at the kick-off meeting.
- The framework for transformative change used in the BioValue project (see Wittmer et al. 2021).
- Pre-existing knowledge about biodiversity and EAI.

Table 4 Questions used for reviewing the chosen guidance documents

<i>Objectives: What is the purpose of integrating biodiversity in EAI?</i>	What is the expected/intended role of EAI in improving biodiversity? (Q1)
	What triggers the inclusion of biodiversity into EAI? (Q2)
<i>Methods: How should biodiversity be integrated in EAI?</i>	How should the significance of biodiversity be assessed in EAI? (Q3+Q4)
	Where in the EAI process is significance of biodiversity decisive? (Q5)
	What types of knowledge should be used when integrating biodiversity in EAI? (Q6+Q7)
	Are synergies and trade-off between biodiversity and other sustainability aspects mentioned, and how should they be handled? (Q8+Q9)
	Which other sustainability aspects are the trade-offs and synergies with? (Q10)
	How should ecosystem services be used in EAI? (Q11+Q12)
<i>Outcome: What is the outcome of integrating biodiversity in EAI?</i>	How should biodiversity impacts be mitigated? (Q13+Q14)
	How should biodiversity be enhanced through EAI? (Q15+Q16)
	How should financial instruments be used to assess or mitigate biodiversity in EAI? (Q17+Q18+Q19+Q20)
	How should biodiversity impacts be monitored? (Q21+Q22)
	What follow-up mechanisms should be in place for biodiversity impacts? (Q23)
<i>Process: How should the process of EAI accommodate the integration of biodiversity?</i>	Where in the EAI process should biodiversity be integrated? (Q24)
	How should biodiversity goals and visions be integrated in EAI? (Q25+Q26)
	How should the SDGs be integrated in EAI and at what level (according to framework)? (Q27+Q28)
	How should the EAI process deal with 'the unknown'/uncertainty concerning biodiversity? (Q29+Q30)
	Who should be involved in the integration of biodiversity in EAI? (Q31)
	How should biodiversity in EAI be linked to spatial planning? (Q32+Q33)

During the review of the documents, any text providing answers to each of the questions was copied into a spreadsheet (example provided below in table 4). This first step yields a large amount of data in the form of text, which was further coded and analysed to develop the benchmark.

The data from the twelve reference documents were further analysed through open coding. Open coding is by Strauss and Corbin summarized as:

“Open coding in grounded theory method is the analytical process by which concepts are identified and developed in terms of their properties and dimensions. The basic analytic procedures by which this is accomplished are: the asking of questions about the data; and the making of comparisons for similarities and differences between each incident, event and other instance of phenomena” (Strauss and Corbin 1990 as cited in Flick 2006, p. 300).

Thus, the purpose of the open coding process is to extract concepts from data.

The coding involved ‘initial coding’, ‘coding’ and ‘coding per document’. In the initial coding the larger paragraphs of text were summarized into shorter paragraphs in order to make it possible to form an overview. In the next coding, the smaller paragraphs were synthesised into single statements to identify concepts to make it possible to compare these across the documents (Watt Boolsen, 2010). Finally, an overview of the concepts per document was provided. The coding process from beginning to end has been guided by the questions in table 4.

To illustrate how the coding was conducted, Table 5 presents an example of the coding process of the data. The first column are the direct quotes from the guidance documents, which is then coded in the following columns as described.

Table 5 Illustration of coding sequence of the guidance documents

Q14: How should biodiversity impacts be mitigated?	Initial coding	Coding	Coding per document
<p><i>Under scoping: Consideration of mitigation and/or enhancement measures: The purpose of mitigation in EIA is to look for ways to achieve the project objectives while avoiding negative impacts or reducing them to acceptable levels. The purpose of enhancement is to look for ways of optimizing environmental benefits. Both mitigation and enhancement of impacts should strive to ensure that the public or individuals do not bear costs, which are greater than the benefits that accrue to them (CBD, 2006 p 10)</i></p>	<p>Avoiding negative impacts or reducing them to acceptable levels. Both mitigation and enhancement of impacts should strive to ensure that the public or individuals do not bear costs, which are greater than the benefits that accrue to them.</p>	<p>Avoidance Reduction/minimization</p>	<p>Avoidance Reduction/minimization Compensation Analysing residual impacts Using mitigation hierarchy Limits to compensation</p>

<p><i>Under scoping: Remedial action can take several forms, i.e. avoidance (or prevention), mitigation (by considering changes to the scale, design, location, siting, process, sequencing, phasing, management and/or monitoring of the proposed activity, as well as restoration or rehabilitation of sites), and compensation (often associated with residual impacts after prevention and mitigation). A ‘positive planning approach’ should be used, where avoidance has priority and compensation is used as a last resort measure. One should acknowledge that compensation will not always be possible: there are cases where it is appropriate to reject a development proposal on grounds of irreversible damage to, or irreplaceable loss of, biodiversity. (CBD, 2006 p 10)</i></p>	<p>avoidance (or prevention), mitigation, compensation (often associated with residual impacts after prevention and mitigation). Avoidance has priority and compensation is used as a last resort measure. Compensation will not always be possible: there are cases where it is appropriate to reject a development proposal on grounds of irreversible damage to, or irreplaceable loss of, biodiversity.</p>	<p>Avoidance Reduction/minimization Compensation/off-setting Analysing residual impacts Using mitigation hierarchy Limits to compensation</p>	
<p><i>In scoping: Define possible measures to avoid, minimize or compensate for significant damage to, or loss of, biodiversity and/or ecosystem services; define possibilities to enhance biodiversity. Make reference to any legal requirements; (CBD, 2006 p 12)</i></p>	<p>Measures to avoid, minimize or compensate for significant damage to, or loss of, biodiversity and/or ecosystem services</p>	<p>Avoidance Reduction/minimization Compensating/off-setting</p>	
<p><i>Alternatives and/or mitigation measures must be identified and described in detail, including an analysis of their likely success and realistic potential to offset adverse project impacts (CBD, 2006 p 12)</i></p>	<p>Mitigation measures must be identified and described in detail, including an analysis of their likely success and realistic potential to offset adverse project impacts</p>	<p>Analysing residual impacts</p>	

The coding or concepts per document were shaped into the benchmark. Here, the concepts are seen as the recommendations from each guidance document connected to the questions in table 4, and thus what future EAs should be measured against and aspire to. Thus, the concepts largely make up the elements in the benchmark.

Some of the questions in table 4 were not made into a benchmark, for example Q1, as it was not deemed relevant to measure and compare the intended role of the integration of biodiversity. Also, where deemed relevant, concepts were grouped differently into the benchmark than in the original framework in table 4. This process of shaping the benchmark based on the analysis and derived concepts was supported by review and discussion in the project team.

6. Test of the Benchmark for integration of biodiversity in EAI, at 200 EAs from Denmark, Germany, Spain and Portugal

This chapter has been developed in a later process, where 200 EAs from Denmark, Germany, Spain and Portugal have been analysed, using the benchmark for integration of biodiversity developed in the first version of the deliverable. The chapter therefore has the character of a report including methodology for selection of reports and operationalisation of the benchmark

6.1. EA Reports Reviewed

The review consisted of 201 EA reports, totalling 120 from Denmark, 20 from Spain, 20 from Germany and 41 from Portugal. Of the 120 Danish reports, 10 reports (7 SEAs and 3 EIAs) did not include any assessments of nature nor biodiversity and have therefore been excluded from the analysis, resulting in a total of 110 Danish EA reports, and 191 EA reports in total for all four countries. The distribution of SEAs, EIAs and a combination of the two is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The distribution of EA reports according to SEA, EIA or combined EIA/SEA, in absolute number and relative to all national reports (in brackets)

Country	SEA reports	EIA reports	Combined EIA/SEA reports	Total
Denmark	44 (40%)	50 (45%)	16 (15%)	110
Spain	12 (60%)	8 (40%)	0	20
Germany	10 (50%)	10 (50%)	0	20
Portugal	21 (49%)	20 (51%)	0	41

For the benchmark analysis described in this report, the combined EIA/SEA reports from Denmark have been distributed according to the level with the highest degree of details, which in the case for 15 reports is EIA and for one report is SEA. The analysis of the Danish reports is therefore divided into 45 SEAs and 65 EIAs.

The distribution of the reports according to their year of publication is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The distribution of SEA and EIA reports according to the year of publication.

Table 7 shows the level of planning at which the EA reports for each country pertain to. The numbers do not necessarily equal the total number of reports presented in Table 1, as some reports pertain to multiple levels of planning. For example, 2 Danish EA reports pertain both to the municipality and the state.

Table 7: The distribution of SEAs and EIAs according to the level of authority on municipal, provincial, regional, or state levels, in absolute numbers and percentage of reports within the national EA type. Note reports covering more than one level of authority are counted at all levels.

Country		Municipal	Provincial	Regional	State
Denmark	SEA	37 (82%)	0	0	8 (18%)
	EIA	32 (49%)	0	1 (2%)	34 (52%)
Spain	SEA	4 (33%)	4 (33%)	3 (25%)	1 (8%)
	EIA				8 (100%)
Germany	SEA	12 (57%)	0	4 (19%)	5 (24%)
	EIA	2 (10%)	0	9 (45%)	9 (45%)
Portugal	SEA	2 (20%)	0	6 (60%)	3 (30%)
	EIA	9 (90%)	0	0	1 (10%)
Total	SEA	55 (63%)	4 (5%)	13 (15%)	17 (19%)
	EIA	43 (42%)	0	10 (10%)	52 (50%)

Table 8 divides the reports according to project and plan types, distinguishing between EIAs pertaining to linear infrastructure or covering large geographic areas, and SEAs for comprehensive or local area plans as well as programmes not geographically associated. The results also distinguish between whether the respective project or plan/programme is located on land or on sea. Note that the numbers do not necessarily equal the total amount of reports stated in Table 1, as one report can be both on-shore and off-shore.

Table 8: The distribution of EA reports according to plan and project types.

			Denmark	Spain	Germany	Portugal	
EIA	Linear infrastructure	Roads (17)	14	1	1	1	
		On land (42)	11		2	1	
		Cables (9)	8			1	
		Pipelines (2)			2		
	On sea (8)	Raw materials (5)	4		1		
		Railways (1)	1				
		Cables (1)	1				
		Bridge (1)			1		
	Projects with large area coverage	On land (49)	Photovoltaic projects (29)	19	5	1	4
			Coastal protection (6)	5	1		
Industrial complex and recreation (3)						3	
Agriculture (4)						4	
Building (2)						2	
Port (1)						1	
On sea (12)	Wind energy projects (4)		1	2	1		
	Coastal protection (5)	4					
	Port (3)	5			3		
SEA	Comprehensive plans	Overall spatial plans (41)	21	11	3	6	
		On land (45)			2	1	
		Agricultural policy (1)				1	
		On sea (5)		1	1	1	
	Local area plans	On land (26)	Local plans (23)	16			7
			Electricity transmission (1)				1
			Climate action (1)			1	1
		On sea (7)	Wind energy projects (2)	2			
			Coastal protection (4)	4			
			Nature protection (1)	1			
Programmes	Non-geographic (3)	N/A		2	1		
	On land (4)	Regional (2)			2		
		Transboundary cooperation (2)		1	1		
			117	21	20	43	

6.2. Benchmark analysis

The following analysis builds upon indicators described in a BioValue report titled, “Benchmark for integration of biodiversity in Environmental Assessment Instruments”. The report provides a benchmark aimed at guiding best practice in the integration of biodiversity in EA and is meant as a tool to support EIA and SEA as “instruments to mitigate the impacts of development activities on biodiversity and ecosystems to promote cross-sectoral approaches constructing pathways towards sustainability...” (Larsen et al. 2022, p. 7).

Drawing upon a selection of guidance documents on the integration of biodiversity impacts, the benchmark identifies 10 themes consisting of various indicators that help to inform the degree to which EAs comply with recommended best practice (Larsen et al. 2022).

Eight of these themes have been selected for the analysis presented in this report. They are as follows: 1. significance, 2. knowledge, 3. synergies and trade-offs, 4. ecosystem services, 5. goals and visions, 6. uncertainty, 7. mitigation and enhancement, and 8. monitoring and follow-up. In this chapter, the compliance of the 191 EA reports (from Denmark, Spain, Portugal, and Germany) in terms of identified indicators under each of the eight themes is analysed and presented.

The themes and indicators are briefly introduced, as well as the relevant elements under each indicator, followed by the results of the analysis. For more details on the rationale behind each indicator, please refer to the benchmark report (Larsen et al. 2022).

For the ease of reading, all numbers are in percentages of the total national number of reports for SEA, EIA and total. The totals are presented in tables in brackets.

Evaluation of the significance of biodiversity impacts

Evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts refers to determining how severe the impact of an activity is expected to be. Especially relevant is the transparency of the approach used in making the evaluation, and thus, the two benchmark indicators for evaluating significance refers to methodology used (indicator B1) and the types of parameters brought into the evaluation (indicator B2).

B1 - Indicator: *What methodology is used to evaluate the significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?*

Evaluating significance is a crucial and challenging point in any EA process. As found in the BioValue benchmark, different methodologies have been deemed relevant for significance evaluation. The three principal methodologies are characterised by a comparison of a biodiversity impact:

- *to reference situation/0-alternative.*
- *against thresholds, criteria, and targets.*
- *to sensitivity of impacted entity.*

RESULTS

Table 9 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two or all three of the methodologies and Table 10 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the methodologies. The more methodologies used, the better.

Table 9: The frequency with which the elements for indicator B1 are present in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No methodology	One methodology	Two methodologies	Three methodologies
Denmark	SEA	27	42	20	11
	EIA	6	26	34	34
	Total	15	33	28	25
Spain	SEA	33	67	0	0
	EIA	0	100	0	0
	Total	20	80	0	0
Portugal**	SEA	0	52	38	0
	EIA	0	60	35	0
	Total	0	56	37	0
Germany	SEA	0	40	50	20
	EIA	0	50	40	10
	Total	0	45	45	10

Table 10: The extent to which the EA reports comply with the elements for indicator B1. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Compare impacts to reference situation/0-alternative	Compare impacts against thresholds, criteria, and targets	Compare impacts to sensitivity of impacted entity
Denmark	SEA	60	31	24
	EIA	69	58	68
	Total	65	47	50
Spain*	SEA	58	0	8
	EIA	100	0	0
	Total	75	0	5
Portugal**	SEA	95	38	5
	EIA	95	15	20
	Total	95	27	12
Germany	SEA	80	30	60
	EIA	60	30	70
	Total	70	30	65

*Other SEA:1, EIA:3, (4)

**2 EIAs have another reference for the evaluation of significance of biodiversity impacts

B2 - Indicator: Which types of parameters are relevant for evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?

Assessing the significance of biodiversity impacts can include different parameters such as extinction risk, resilience, impact characteristics (e.g., size, frequency, duration), and sensitivity of the affected areas or entities. The parameters thus fall into two categories, those:

- *Related to characteristics of the activity/impact on biodiversity.*
- *Related to characteristics of the impacted biodiversity entities.*

RESULTS

In table 11 it can be seen how many EA reports include either no, one or two parameters for evaluating significance. In Table 12, it can be seen how many EA reports include each of the two elements.

Table 11: The % of reports with parameters described in the evaluation of significance of biodiversity impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No parameter	One parameter	Two parameters
Denmark	SEA	29	24	47
	EIA	8	14	78
	Total	16	18	65
Spain	SEA	33	58	8
	EIA	0	100	0
	Total	20	75	5
Portugal	SEA	0	81	14
	EIA	10	50	40
	Total	5	66	27
Germany	SEA	10	60	60
	EIA	0	0	100
	Total	5	30	80

Table 12: The frequency with which different parameters are described in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Parameters related to characteristic of the activity/impact on biodiversity	Parameters related to characteristic of the impacted biodiversity areas/entities
Denmark	SEA	71	47
	EIA	89	82
	Total	82	67
Spain	SEA	67	8
	EIA	100	0
	Total	80	5
Portugal	SEA	33	86
	EIA	90	40
	Total	61	63
Germany	SEA	50	80
	EIA	100	90
	Total	75	85

Knowledge used for integrating biodiversity

Understanding the knowledge that is used in the EA can help ensure the quality of the information being produced and thereby, what knowledge is represented as decision-support. The theme of knowledge consists of one indicator referring to the different types of knowledge referenced in the assessment of biodiversity impacts (indicator C1).

C1 - Indicator: Which types of knowledge is used for working with biodiversity in the EA?

Knowledge as referred to in the benchmark distinguishes between three types, namely:

- *Expert knowledge.*
- *Multidisciplinary knowledge.*
- *Local and indigenous knowledge.*

Here it is important to note that multidisciplinary knowledge is defined as knowledge from different basic disciplines such as natural science and social science – not different disciplines e.g. within natural science.

RESULTS

In, it is shown how many EA reports comply with none, one, two or all three of the types of knowledge and Table 14 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the elements.

Table 13: The % of reports of different types of knowledge used when working with biodiversity in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No types	One type	Two types	Three types
Denmark	SEA	0	73	27	0
	EIA	0	40	60	0
	Total	0	54	46	0
Spain	SEA	100	0	0	0
	EIA	88	13	0	0
	Total	95*	5	0	0
Portugal	SEA	10	29	62	0
	EIA	10	10	80	0
	Total	10	20	71	0
Germany	SEA	0	90	10	0
	EIA	0	100	0	0
	Total	0	95	5	0

* For the 19 with no elements, types of knowledge are not specified, as derived from the text by assessing the indicators and parameters used. Multidisciplinary knowledge is usually required to comply with the requirements of EIA/SEA legislation in Spain, because of the wide array of topics that need to be covered. Use of multidisciplinary knowledge might be practice, without mentioning in the reports.

Table 14: The % of studied EA reports (both SEA and EIA) to use the three different types of knowledge.

		Expert knowledge	Multidisciplinary knowledge	Local and indigenous knowledge
Denmark	SEA	100	0	27
	EIA	100	2	58
	Total	100	1	45
Spain	SEA	0	0	0
	EIA	0	13	0
	Total	0	5	0
Portugal	SEA	76	76	0
	EIA	80	90	0
	Total	78	83	0
Germany	SEA	80	20	10
	EIA	100	0	0
	Total	90	10	5

Handling of synergies and trade-offs

Due to the complex nature of impacts, their significant number in plan/project development, and the multidisciplinary nature of sustainability (social, cultural, economic, and environmental), synergies and trade-offs become an inevitability of EA. Understanding the ways in which the synergies and trade-offs associated with biodiversity are managed in EA (indicator D1) is therefore an important part of plan and project development.

D1 - Indicator: *How are synergies and trade-off between biodiversity and other sustainability aspects handled in the EA?*

Synergies and trade-offs refer to the respectively positive and negative correlation that one impacts may have with other impacts. Managing these within EA refers to the following elements:

- *Acknowledging that synergies and trade-offs exist.*
- *Identifying synergies and trade-offs.*
- *Managing synergies and trade-offs (if relevant).*
- *Taking trade-offs into account in decision-making (if relevant).*

RESULTS

Table 15 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two, three or all four of the approaches and Table 16 shows how many EA reports comply with each of these approaches.

Table 15: The extent to which synergies and trade-offs are managed in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No elements	One element	Two elements	Three elements	Four elements
Denmark	SEA	78	2	18	2	0
	EIA	83	6	11	0	0
	Total	81	5	14	1	0
Spain	SEA	33	33	33	0	0
	EIA	13	88	0	0	0
	Total	75	55	20	0	0
Portugal	SEA	57	19	24	0	0
	EIA	85	10	5	0	0
	Total	71	15	15	0	0
Germany	SEA	40	20	10	20	0
	EIA	30	20	50	0	0
	Total	35	20	30	10	0

Table 16: The frequency with which the elements are used to describe synergies and trade-offs in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		It is acknowledged that synergies and trade-offs exist	Synergies and trade-offs are identified	Synergies and trade-offs are managed	Trade-offs and synergies and taken into account in decision-making
Denmark	SEA	22	20	0	2
	EIA	17	11	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	19	15	0	1
Spain	SEA	67	33	0	0
	EIA	38	25	25	0
	<i>Total</i>	55	30	10	0
Portugal	SEA	43	24	0	0
	EIA	15	0	0	5
	<i>Total</i>	29	12	0	2
Germany	SEA	40	50	10	30
	EIA	60	60	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	50	55	5	15

Use of ecosystem service

Conserving an ecosystem's structure and function is crucial for preserving the ecosystem services it can provide. EAs should be an opportunity for identifying and evaluating the functionality of these services. Determining how ecosystem services are used in EA is therefore Indicator E1.

E1- Indicator: *How are ecosystem services used in the EA?*

Using ecosystem services can range from recognizing their presence to actively trying to preserve them. The following eight elements are identified in terms of ecosystem services:

- *Mentioning ecosystem services*
- *Acknowledging the importance of ecosystem services.*
- *Mapping ecosystem services.*
- *Identifying users/beneficiaries of ecosystem services.*
- *Assigning values to ecosystem services.*
- *Evaluating impacts on ecosystem services from the activities.*
- *Mitigating impacts on ecosystem services (if relevant).*
- *Monitoring ecosystem services (if relevant).*

RESULTS

Table 17 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two, three or four of the elements. Despite there being eight elements, no report complied with more than four of them. Table 18 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the elements.

Table 17: The % of EA reports complying with none, one, two, three or four of the eight elements associated with using ecosystem services. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No elements	One element	Two elements	Three elements	Four elements
Denmark	SEA	100	0	0	0	0
	EIA	94	3	2	2	0
	Total	96	2	1	1	0
Spain	SEA	42	0	50	8	0
	EIA	100	0	0	0	0
	Total	65	0	30	5	0
Portugal	SEA	10	29	62	0	0
	EIA	10	10	80	0	0
	Total	10	20	71	0	0
Germany	SEA	70	0	10	10	10
	EIA	50	40	10	0	0
	Total	60	20	10	5	5

Table 18: The % of EA reports complying with each ecosystem service element. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Mentioning	Acknowledging	Mapping	Identifying	Assigning value	Evaluating	Mitigating	Monitoring
Denmark	SEA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	EIA	6	0	3	0	0	1	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	4	0	2	0	0	0	1	0
Spain	SEA	58	42	0	0	8	17	0	0
	EIA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	35	25	0	0	5	10	0	0
Portugal	SEA	43	24	5	10	0	10	0	0
	EIA	10	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	27	15	2	7	0	5	0	0
Germany	SEA	30	30	0	20	10	0	0	0
	EIA	40	0	0	0	0	0	10	0
	<i>Total</i>	35	15	0	10	5	0	5	0

Integration of biodiversity goals and visions

Having a vision for the integration of biodiversity helps ensure integration aimed at existing policies and targets set at different levels of policymaking. The related indicator (F1) is different approaches to integrating biodiversity goals and visions in EA.

F1- Indicator: *How are biodiversity goals and visions integrated in the EA?*

The different approaches to integrating biodiversity goals and visions are as follows:

- *Through including conservation priorities and targets from EU Biodiversity Strategy, National biodiversity strategies or other existing guidance documents (e.g., international, and national, regional, and local laws, policies, plans and strategies) in Action plans.*
- *Deciding on a 'vision', with explicit goals, objectives, desired outcomes.*
- *Through applying an ecosystem-based approach.*

RESULTS

Table 19 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two and three of the approaches to integrating biodiversity goals and targets and table 20 shows how many EA reports exhibit the various approaches.

Table 19: The % of EA reports that comply with either none, one, two or three of the approaches to integrating biodiversity goals and visions. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No approaches	One approach	Two approaches	Three approaches
Denmark	SEA	80	20	0	0
	EIA	80	20	0	0
	Total	80	20	0	0
Spain	SEA	50	50	0	0
	EIA	88	13	0	0
	Total	65	35	0	0
Portugal	SEA	43	43	14	0
	EIA	55	45	0	0
	Total	49	44	7	0
Germany	SEA	10	80	10	0
	EIA	60	40	0	0
	Total	35	60	5	0

Table 20: The % of times each approach is exhibited in the EA reports. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Including existing priorities and targets	Deciding on a 'vision'	Applying an ecosystem-based approach
Denmark	SEA	16	4	0
	EIA	20	0	0
	Total	18	2	0
Spain	SEA	33	0	0
	EIA	13	25	0
	Total	25	10	0
Portugal	SEA	24	48	0
	EIA	45	0	0
	Total	34	24	0
Germany	SEA	70	30	0
	EIA	40	0	0
	Total	55	15	0

Handling of uncertainty

Uncertainty in making assessments on biodiversity and decisions therefrom can have significant consequences for the biodiversity it otherwise aims to protect. The theme of handling uncertainty therefore consists of one indicator on determining how an EA process handles this uncertainty throughout the EA report (Indicator G1).

G1 - Indicator: How does the EA process deal with uncertainty concerning biodiversity?

Handling uncertainty can be a matter of the transparency of knowledge and data, taking the precautionary approach, and ensuring strategies that minimize the risk of uncertainties.

- *Ensure transparency about lack of data, gaps in knowledge, and uncertainty.*
- *Take a precautionary approach to impacts.*
- *Identify gaps in knowledge and gather additional information (if relevant)*
- *Manage uncertainty e.g. using adaptive management, scenarios etc. (if relevant)*

Of the original four elements listed above, researchers from Portugal identified two new approaches to managing uncertainty, that are not included in the original benchmark (Larsen et al. 2023). These two approaches have been included in the analysis of the 41 Portuguese reports, but not for the remaining countries. The two approaches are as follows:

- *Through establishing follow-up with guidelines (planning, management, monitoring, incl. monitoring indicators)*
- *Through engaging different stakeholders throughout the EA process*

RESULTS

Table 21 shows the number of reports complying with no, one, two, three or four approaches to managing uncertainty. No reports used more than four out of six possible approaches.

Table 22 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the approaches.

Table 21: The distribution of EA reports according to their compliance with no, one, two, three or four approaches for managing uncertainty. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No approaches	One approach	Two approaches	Three approaches	Four approaches
Denmark	SEA	84	11	4	0	0
	EIA	52	29	12	5	2
	Total	65	22	9	3	1
Spain	SEA	8	75	17	0	0
	EIA	88	13	0	0	0
	Total	40	55	10	0	0
Portugal	SEA	76	14	5	5	5
	EIA	70	25	0	0	0
	Total	73	20	2	2	2
Germany	SEA	0	70	20	0	10
	EIA	20	70	10	0	0
	Total	10	70	15	0	5

Table 22: The % of EA reports referencing the different approaches to managing uncertainty. Note that only the Portuguese reports have been analysed using the last two parameters. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Ensure transparency	Take a precautionary approach	Identify gaps in knowledge and gather information	Manage uncertainty	Through establishing follow-up with guidelines	Through engaging different stakeholders throughout the EA process
Denmark	SEA	13	4	2	0	--	--
	EIA	38	22	8	6	--	--
	Total	28	15	6	4	--	--
Spain	SEA	8	92	17	8	--	--
	EIA	0	13	13	0	--	--
	Total	5	60	15	5	--	--
Portugal	SEA	0	14	0	5	19	10
	EIA	20	0	10	5	0	0
	Total	10	7	5	5	10	5
Germany	SEA	70	30	30	20	--	--
	EIA	70	10	10	0	--	--
	Total	70	20	20	10	--	--

--: The last parameters were developed in relation to the Portuguese cases, and thus not evaluated for the other countries.

Biodiversity mitigation and enhancement

Mitigating negative impacts on biodiversity and enhancing positive impacts is a central component of the EA process. This theme is divided into three indicators: how biodiversity impacts are mitigated (Indicator I1), the degree to which they are mitigated (Indicator I2), and the financial instruments used to support the implementation of the mitigation measures (Indicator I3). The analysis is supported by identifying which words are used to describe the mitigation in question and which plan/project phase the mitigation is expected to take place.

I1- Indicator: *How are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?*

The way in which impacts are mitigated is a matter of the frame of reference used, such as the mitigation hierarchy, analysis of residual impacts, and considering biodiversity values. The analysis consists of the following elements:

- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated in accordance with the mitigation hierarchy.*
- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated based on analysis of residual impacts.*
- *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated through enhancing biodiversity values.*

RESULTS

Table 23 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two and three of the approaches for mitigating biodiversity impacts. Table 24 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the three approaches.

Table 23: The extent to which the EA reports comply with either none, one, two or three of the mitigation approaches. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No approach	One approach	Two approaches	Three approaches
Denmark	SEA	84	16	0	0
	EIA	71	20	5	2
	Total	76	18	5	1
Spain	SEA	50	50	0	0
	EIA	63	25	13	0
	Total	55	40	5	0
Portugal	SEA	95	5	0	0
	EIA	5	80	15	0
	Total	51	41	7	0
Germany	SEA	20	80	0	0
	EIA	0	100	0	0
	Total	10	90	0	0

Table 24: The % of reports utilizing each mitigation approach. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Biodiversity impacts are mitigated in accordance with the mitigation hierarchy	Biodiversity impacts are mitigated based on analysis of residual	Biodiversity impacts are mitigated through enhancing biodiversity values
Denmark	SEA	2	4	9
	EIA	20	11	9
	Total	13	8	9
Spain	SEA	50	0	0
	EIA	13	13	13
	Total	35	5	5
Portugal	SEA	5	0	0
	EIA	95	0	15
	Total	49	0	7
Germany	SEA	50	0	30
	EIA	100	0	0
	Total	75	0	15

12 – Indicator: *To what degree are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?*

The degree to which biodiversity impacts are mitigated refers to the frame of reference that is used in determining the residual impact following the implementation of the mitigation measure. The two frames of reference are as follows:

3. *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that ‘no net loss’ is achieved.*
4. *Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that ‘net gain’ is achieved.*

These references should be interpreted such that reference 2, where a ‘net gain’ is achieved, is considered better than reference 1, focussing on ‘no net loss’. To comply with the two elements, it must be stated explicitly in the report e.g. that mitigation has been appointed to reach either ‘no net loss’ or ‘net gain’. An example of ‘no net loss’ is that ecological functionality has been maintained.

RESULTS

In Table 25, it is shown how many EA reports comply with none, one and two of the frames of reference and in Table 26, it is shown how many EA reports comply with each of the elements.

Table 25: The % of EA reports complying with no, one or both frames of reference for mitigating biodiversity impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No frame of reference	One frame of reference	Two frames of reference
Denmark	SEA	96	4	0
	EIA	89	11	0
	Total	92	8	0
Spain	SEA	75	25	0
	EIA	13	88	0
	Total	50	50	0
Portugal	SEA	95	5	0
	EIA	10	80	10
	Total	54	41	5
Germany	SEA	30	50	20
	EIA	10	80	10
	Total	20	65	15

Table 26: The number of reports for each frame of reference for mitigating biodiversity impacts.

		Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that 'no net loss' is achieved	Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that 'net gain' is achieved
Denmark	SEA	2	2
	EIA	8	3
	Total	5	3
Spain	SEA	8	17
	EIA	63	25
	Total	30	20
Portugal	SEA	5	0
	EIA	85	15
	Total	44	7
Germany	SEA	60	30
	EIA	90	10
	Total	75	20

I3 – Indicator: *How is the implementation of mitigation supported by financial instruments?*

Mitigation measures require the support of financial instruments to ensure their implementation. This indicator consists of three approaches to describing the prescribed financial instruments:

- *The necessary financial settings for implementation of mitigation measures incl. compensation/off-setting are established (if relevant).*
- *Financial incentives are provided for proponents to protect biodiversity (if relevant).*
- *Financial settings for maintenance of biodiversity are established (if relevant).*

RESULTS

In Table 27, it can be seen how many EA reports comply with no, one, two or three approaches to describing the financial instruments intended to support the implementation of mitigation measures.

Table 27: The % of EA reports exhibiting either no, one, two or three approaches to describing the intended financial instruments. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No approach	One approach	Two approaches	Three approaches
Denmark	SEA	100	0	0	0
	EIA	100	0	0	0
	Total	100	0	0	0
Spain	SEA	100	0	0	0
	EIA	25	75	0	0
	Total	70	30	0	0
Portugal	SEA	100	0	0	0
	EIA	100	0	0	0
	Total	100	0	0	0
Germany	SEA	80	20	0	0
	EIA	100	0	0	0
	Total	90	10	0	0

Table 28: The % of EA reports complying with the three approaches to ensuring financial instruments. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		The necessary financial settings for the implementation of mitigation measures incl. compensation/off-setting are established	Financial incentives are provided for proponents to protect biodiversity	Financial settings for maintenance of biodiversity are established
Denmark	SEA	0	0	0
	EIA	0	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	0	0	0
Spain	SEA	0	0	0
	EIA	75	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	30	0	0
Portugal	SEA	0	0	0
	EIA	0	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	0	0	0
Germany	SEA	20	0	0
	EIA	0	0	0
	<i>Total</i>	10	0	0

I4 indicator: *How are the mitigation measures worded?*

The wording used to describe the mitigation measure indicates the commitment granted to implementing the mitigation measure. The different words are described as the following:

- *As a 'can be implemented'*
- *As a 'should be implemented'*
- *As a 'must be implemented'*

RESULTS

Table 29 shows how many EA reports use 'can', 'should', and 'must' when describing the implementation of the mitigation measure.

Table 29: The distribution of the EA reports according to the wording used to describe the implementation of the mitigation measure. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		As a 'can be implemented'	As a 'should be implemented'	As a 'must be implemented'
Denmark	SEA	22	4	27
	EIA	25	9	52
	Total	24	7	42
Spain	SEA	0	83	8
	EIA	0	63	63
	Total	0	75	30
Portugal	SEA	5	0	0
	EIA	40	40	15
	Total	22	20	7
Germany	SEA	40	30	10
	EIA	60	10	40
	Total	50	20	25

I5-indicator: Which phase of the project is the mitigation measure directed towards?

The mitigation measure can be applied to different phases of the plan/project, such as:

- *Construction*
- *Operation*
- *Decommissioning*

RESULTS

Table 30 shows how many EA reports apply mitigation measures in the construction, operation and/or decommissioning phase.

Table 30: The % of EA reports referring to mitigation measures to lessen impacts in the construction, operation and/or decommissioning phases of the plan/project. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Construction	Operation	Decommissioning
Denmark	SEA	11	31	2
	EIA	62	51	6
	Total	41	43	5
Spain	SEA	0	0	67
	EIA	100	100	63
	Total	40	40	65
Portugal	SEA	5	5	0
	EIA	95	25	0
	Total	49	15	0
Germany	SEA	100	90	0
	EIA	20	20	10
	Total	60	55	5

Monitoring and follow-up on biodiversity impacts

Monitoring in EA refers to establishing a plan for following up on the predicted impacts, their significance, and on the implementation of mitigation measures. This theme consists of three indicators: the specification of monitoring in EA (Indicator J1), the aim of the monitoring program (Indicator J2), the specified use of the monitored data (Indicator J3). Like for the mitigation and enhancement theme, this analysis is supplemented by the wording used to describe the commitment to the established monitoring.

J1 - Indicator: *How does the EA specify monitoring of biodiversity impacts?*

Specifying the projected monitoring in an EA is categorized into the following elements:

- *There are plans to establish monitoring of biodiversity impacts.*
- *Clear targets, indicators, and responsibilities for monitoring of biodiversity impacts are specified.*
- *Plans for monitoring are linked to sound baseline information.*
- *Plans for monitoring specify that stakeholders should be involved.*

RESULTS

Table 31 shows how many EA reports comply with none, one, two, three or all the elements and Table 32 shows how many EA reports comply with each of the elements.

Table 31: The % of EA reports that comply with either none, one, two, three or four elements for monitoring impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No elements	One element	Two elements	Three elements	Four elements
Denmark	SEA	91	9	0	0	0
	EIA	78	9	12	0	0
	Total	84	9	7	0	0
Spain	SEA	0	58	33	8	0
	EIA	0	100	0	0	0
	Total	0	75	20	5	0
Portugal	SEA	29	33	33	5	0
	EIA	45	30	10	15	0
	Total	37	32	22	10	0
Germany	SEA	20	40	40	0	0
	EIA	30	50	20	0	0
	Total	25	45	30	0	0

Table 32: The % of EA reports complying with each monitoring element. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		There are plans to establish monitoring	Clear targets, indicators, and responsibilities for monitoring	Plans for monitoring are linked to sound baseline information	Plans for monitoring specify that stakeholders should be involved
Denmark	SEA	9	0	0	0
	EIA	22	9	3	0
	Total	16	5	2	0
Spain	SEA	100	8	0	8
	EIA	75	0	0	0
	Total	90	5	0	5
Portugal	SEA	67	19	24	5
	EIA	55	20	20	0
	Total	61	20	22	2
Germany	SEA	70	20	10	20
	EIA	70	10	10	0
	Total	70	15	10	10

J2 - Indicator: What is the monitoring of biodiversity impacts specified in the EA aimed at?

The following indicator describes what monitoring efforts outlined in the EA are aimed at, distinguishing between the following:

- *Validating the predicted biodiversity impacts.*
- *Validating the outcomes of mitigation measures.*

Based on the analysis of the EAs from Portugal, a third aim was identified and included in the analysis of the 41 Portuguese reports.

- *Identify strategic changes not initially foreseen - e.g., changes in the SRF, in the planning implementation, etc.*

For the reports to comply with the aims, the aim of monitoring had to be explicitly mentioned.

RESULTS

In Table 33, it is shown how many EA reports comply with none, one and two of the aims of monitoring efforts. Table 34 shows how many EA reports target monitoring at each of the aims.

Table 33: The % of EA reports specifying either no, one, two or three of aims of monitoring biodiversity impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No aims	One aim	Two aims	Three aims
Denmark	SEA	96	4	0	--
	EIA	75	12	12	--
	Total	84	9	7	--
Spain	SEA	0	33	67	--
	EIA	0	13	88	--
	Total	0	25	75	--
Portugal	SEA	38	24	10	29
	EIA	45	20	35	0
	Total	41	22	22	15
Germany	SEA	70	30	0	--
	EIA	60	30	10	--
	Total	65	30	5	--

--: The last parameter was developed in relation to the Portuguese cases, and thus not evaluated for the other countries.

Table 34: The % of reports explicitly specifying the aim of monitoring of biodiversity impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Validating the predicted biodiversity impacts	Validating the outcomes of mitigation measures	Identify strategic changes not initially foreseen
Denmark	SEA	2	2	--
	EIA	12	25	--
	Total	8	15	--
Spain	SEA	92	75	--
	EIA	88	100	--
	Total	90	85	--
Portugal	SEA	52	52	29
	EIA	55	35	0
	Total	54	44	15
Germany	SEA	30	0	--
	EIA	20	30	--
	Total	25	15	--

--: The last parameter was developed in relation to the Portuguese cases, and thus not evaluated for the other countries.

J3 – Indicator: *What does the EA specify that monitoring of biodiversity should be used for?*

The specification of what monitoring biodiversity impacts will be used for is important for realizing the monitoring in practice. The associated purposes are as follows:

- *Implementing adaptive management.*
- *Building knowledge for future EAs and planning.*
- *Checking compliance with conditions for approval.*

RESULTS

Table 35 shows the number of reports that specify no, one, two or three purposes for which monitoring of biodiversity will be used for. Table 36 shows how many reports explicitly mention each purpose.

Table 35: The % of reports specifying no, one, two or three purposes for which monitoring biodiversity impacts will be used. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		No purpose	One purpose	Two purposes	Three purposes
Denmark	SEA	98	2	0	0
	EIA	88	8	5	0
	Total	92	5	3	0
Spain	SEA	8	83	8	0
	EIA	38	63	0	0
	Total	20	75	5	0
Portugal	SEA	43	48	5	5
	EIA	45	20	30	5
	Total	44	34	17	5
Germany	SEA	50	50	0	0
	EIA	80	20	0	0
	Total	65	35	0	0

Table 36: The % of reports explicitly stating each of the purposes for which biodiversity impacts will be used. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		Implementing adaptive management	Building knowledge for future EAs and planning	Checking compliance with conditions for approval
Denmark	SEA	0	0	2
	EIA	11	5	2
	Total	6	3	2
Spain	SEA	42	50	0
	EIA	63	0	0
	Total	50	30	0
Portugal*	SEA	52	5	14
	EIA	45	5	45
	Total	49	5	29
Germany*	SEA	50	0	0
	EIA	20	0	0
	Total	35	0	0

J4-indicator: *How are the specifications for monitoring worded?*

The wording used to describe the monitoring can indicate the commitment granted to implementing the mitigation measure. The different words are described as the following:

- *As a 'can be implemented'*
- *As a 'should be implemented'*
- *As a 'must be implemented'*

RESULTS

Table 37 shows how many EA reports use the identified wordings to describe monitoring efforts of biodiversity impacts.

Table 37: The % of reports using the different wordings in association with monitoring biodiversity impacts. % of national reports respectively SEA, EIA and total.

		As 'can be implemented'	As 'should be implemented'	As 'must be implemented'
Denmark	SEA	2	0	0
	EIA	6	9	14
	Total	5	5	8
Spain	SEA	0	83	17
	EIA	13	50	50
	Total	5	70	30
Portugal	SEA	14	38	5
	EIA	0	35	15
	Total	7	37	10
Germany	SEA	10	40	40
	EIA	30	0	10
	Total	20	20	25

6.3. Methodology the analysis of the annex report

The chapter concerns the methodology employed for a systematic analysis of how biodiversity is considered in EIA and SEA reports. The aim has been to map the existing realities of both assessment of biodiversity and the mitigation practices of biodiversity impacts. This is achieved through a selection and text analysis of 200 EIA and SEA cases on spatial planning and related infrastructural developments.

Selection of reports

The environmental assessment reports to be included in the analysis are for plans and projects subject to environmental assessment requirement because of the EIA and the SEA Directive. The sample of reports are to be based on the following selection criteria:

1. Reports relates to activities at sea and activities on land.

The distribution between the two types was aimed for 1:10, which reflects that environmental assessment of activities in the sea territory is still a practice under development.

2. The reports for EIA must cover projects with extensive land use/land conversion.

With this criterion, cases are secured which, in terms of their geographical distribution and extent, will have a potentially significant impact on biodiversity. The criterion is met by choosing cases that are either linear infrastructure projects or projects with extensive land occupation/conversion.

Infrastructure can generally be defined as the connected structural elements that form the framework for society to function (based on Becker-Christensen 2005; Infrastrukturkommissionen 2008). In BioValue, infrastructure projects are defined to be the physical facilities that make up the connections and which, with their linear design, enable the transport of something from one place to another. The project categories chosen are physical transport infrastructure and cables. The latter is a project category in expansion due to the acceleration of renewable energy development.

3. The reports for SEA must covers plans related to spatial planning.

Spatial planning concerns the policies and regulation of land use in a certain geography, being national, regional, or local. Spatial planning is making significant provision for biodiversity through its key role in forming societal activities and defining and setting restrictions for the use of the limited land area.

The SEA reports chosen must cover either overall spatial planning or local level spatial planning.

4. The reports must primarily date 5 years back.

Table 38: Overview of categories of cases.

Type		On land	On Sea
Projects	Linear infrastructure projects	Roads Rails Cables	Cables
	Projects with large area coverage	Photo voltaic projects	Wind energy projects
Plans	Comprehensive plans	Overall spatial plans	Marine spatial plan
	Local area plans	Local plans	Plans for energy islands

Initial text analysis and coding

The reports chosen based on the criteria from section 3.2 was subject to a text analysis and coding. The four participating universities in BioValue were responsible for the initial analysis coding of the country relevant reports, based upon a framework developed by Aalborg University. The final analysis of codes was undertaken by Aalborg University and will be further explicated in section 3.3.

The framework for initial analysis and coding consisted of two parts:

Background data

For each report the following meta-data was registered:

1. Report ID
2. Level of authorities (municipality, province, region, state)
3. Type of report (SEA, EIA)
4. Place (off-shore, on-shore, both)
5. Year of publication

Benchmark data

Template containing themes and indicators from the previously developed benchmark in BioValue for integrating biodiversity in impact assessment (Larsen et al., 2023).

Each report was then reviewed and coded with a focus on registering any text that answers the questions below in table 34. The themes, questions and labels are based on the benchmark developed with a few additions relevant for analysing reports.

Table 39: Framework for benchmark analysis.

Themes	Indicators – formulated as question	Elements
Significance	What methodology is used to evaluate the significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Impacts are compared to reference situation/0-alternative. - Impacts are compared against thresholds, criteria, and targets, and targets. - Impacts are compared to sensitivity of impacted entity.
	Which types of parameters are used for evaluating significance of biodiversity impacts in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parameters related to characteristics of the activity/impact on biodiversity. - Parameters related to characteristics of the impacted biodiversity entities.
Knowledge	Which types of knowledge is used for working with biodiversity in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert knowledge. - Multidisciplinary knowledge. - Local and indigenous knowledge.
Synergies and trade-offs	How are synergies and trade-off between biodiversity and other sustainability aspects handled in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is acknowledged that synergies and trade-offs exist. - Synergies and trade-offs are identified. - Synergies and trade-offs are managed. - Trade-offs are taken into account in decision-making
Ecosystem service	How are ecosystem services used for working with biodiversity in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acknowledging the importance of ecosystem services. - Mapping ecosystem services. - Identifying users/beneficiaries of ecosystem services. - Assigning values to ecosystem services. - Evaluating impacts on ecosystem services from the activities. - Mitigating impacts on ecosystem services - Monitoring ecosystem services
Goals and Visions	How are biodiversity goals and visions integrated in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Through including national and/or international goals and visions as significance criteria - Deciding on a ‘vision’ to which the SEA should contribute, with explicit goals, objectives, desired outcomes for biodiversity.
Uncertainty	How did the EA process deal with ‘the unknown’/uncertainty concerning biodiversity?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Through ensuring transparency about lack of data, gaps in knowledge, and uncertainty - Through taking a precautionary approach to impacts - Through identifying gaps in knowledge and gathering additional information - Through managing uncertainty e.g. using adaptive management, scenarios etc.
Mitigation and enhancement	How are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity impacts are mitigated in accordance with the mitigation hierarchy. - Biodiversity impacts are mitigated based on analysis of residual impacts. - Biodiversity impacts are mitigated through enhancing biodiversity values.
	To what degree are biodiversity impacts mitigated in the EA?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that ‘no net loss’ is achieved. - Biodiversity impacts are mitigated so that ‘net gain’ is achieved.
	How are the mitigation measures worded? (OVP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As a ‘can be implemented’. - As a ‘should be implemented’. - As a ‘must be implemented’?

	<i>Which phase of the project is the mitigation directed towards? (OVP)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construction - Operation - Decommissioning
	<i>How is the implementation of mitigation supported by financial instruments?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The necessary financial settings for implementation of mitigation measures incl. compensation/off-setting are established. - Financial incentives are provided for proponents to protect biodiversity. - Financial settings for maintenance of biodiversity are established
Monitoring and follow-up	<i>How does the EA specify monitoring of biodiversity impacts?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There are plans to establish monitoring of biodiversity impacts. - Clear targets, indicators, and responsibilities for monitoring of biodiversity impacts are specified. - Plans for monitoring are linked to sound baseline information. - Plans for monitoring specify that stakeholders should be involved.
	<i>What is the monitoring of biodiversity impacts specified in the EA aimed at?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validating the predicted biodiversity impacts. - Validating the outcomes of mitigation measures.
	<i>What does the EA specify that monitoring of biodiversity should be used for?</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementing adaptive management. - Building knowledge for future EAs and planning. - Checking compliance with conditions for approval.
	<i>How are the specifications for monitoring worded? (OVP)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As a 'can be implemented'. - As a 'should be implemented'. - As a 'must be implemented'?

The coding entailed the rigorous assessment of the fulfilment status of each criterion, discerning whether it was met or not. A positive affirmation resulted in a coding of (1), whereas a negative outcome was denoted by (0), thus constituting a binary analytical approach. The substantiation of criterion fulfilment was documented through the incorporation of citations extracted from the corresponding report.

7. References

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